

Status report of air quality in Europe for year 2022, using validated data

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Cover design: EEA
Cover image: © Jaime Targa
Layout: EEA / ETC HE

Publication Date:

May 2024
ISBN 978-82-93970-44-6

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Preparation of this report has been funded by the European Environment Agency (EEA) as part of a grant with the European Topic Centre on Human health and the environment (ETC-HE) and expresses the views of the authors. The contents of this publication do not necessarily reflect the position or opinion of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union. Neither the European Environment Agency nor the European Topic Centre on Human health and the environment is liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of the information contained in this publication.

How to cite this report:

Targa, J., Colina, M., Banyuls, L., González Ortiz, A., Soares, J. (2024). *Status report of air quality in Europe for year 2022, using validated data* (ETC-HE Report 2024/3). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment.

The report is available from <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/all-etc-reports> and <https://zenodo.org/communities/eea-etc/?page=1&size=20>.

EEA activity no. 3 Human health and the environment.

ETC-HE coordinator: Stiftelsen NILU, Kjeller, Norway (<https://www.nilu.com>)

ETC-HE consortium partners: Federal Environment Agency/Umweltbundesamt (UBA), Aether Limited, Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI), Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques (INERIS), Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute (Swiss TPH), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO), 4sfera Innova S.L.U., klarFAKTe.U

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Acknowledgements

This report has been produced by the European Topic Centre on Human health and the Environment (ETC HE) in close cooperation with the EEA.

The ETC task manager was Jaume Targa, closely assisted by María Colina and Joana Soares, and the EEA project manager was Alberto González Ortiz closely assisted by Luca Liberti.

Additional EEA contributors were Artur Gsella. Additional ETC HE contributors were Michel Houssiau (under 4sfera Innova), Anna Ripoll (4sfera Innova), Laia Azcón (4sfera Innova) and Rune Ødegård (NILU).

Thanks are due to the air quality data suppliers in the reporting countries for collecting and providing the data on which this report is based, and for providing feedback and comments to the draft report.

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1 Summary

The *2022 Status report of air quality in Europe* presents summarized information on the status of air quality in Europe for the protection of health. It is based on 2022 validated monitoring data⁽¹⁾ officially reported under the Ambient Air Quality Directives in the 2023 September reporting cycle⁽²⁾. It provides information on the following pollutants, regulated by the Ambient Air Quality Directives (AAQD):

- PM₁₀: Particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm or less
- PM_{2.5}: Particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 µm or less
- O₃: Tropospheric ozone
- NO₂: Nitrogen dioxide
- BaP: Benzo[a]pyrene
- SO₂: Sulphur dioxide
- CO: Carbon monoxide
- C₆H₆: Benzene
- As: Arsenic
- Cd: Cadmium
- Pb: Lead
- Ni: Nickel

It also offers a comparison with the situation in previous years.

Data included in this report was received by 05 March 2024 from the reporting countries. By that date the reporting status of 2022 validated data is summarized in Figure 1, where a green box indicates that the referred pollutant was reported by the referred country and a grey box indicates the contrary (that the referred pollutant was not reported by the referred country). Please see editorial notes at the end of this Chapter on additional information on the data used. The number of stations by country reporting each pollutant, with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, is also included in Figure 1, while Table

¹Please be aware that some countries also report official data from modelling applications. Those data are available at <https://eeadmz1-cws-wp-air02.azurewebsites.net/index.php/users-corner/modeling-results-viewer/>

²<https://aqportal.discomap.eea.europa.eu/index.php/reporters-corner/>

3 in the Annex summarizes the number of stations, with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, at different country aggregations. Data from stations that do not fulfil the criteria from Box 1.1 are excluded from this report. Please be aware that the number of stations presented in Figure 1 and Table 3, that corresponds to all reported stations fulfilling the minimum data coverage criteria for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, may be different to the one presented in the corresponding boxplots, as there could be some stations not fulfilling the minimum data coverage criteria for the corresponding aggregation.

Figure 1: Number of stations, for each country and each pollutant, that in 2022 reported data with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, by 05 March 2024

	PM10	PM2.5	O3	NO2	BaP	SO2	CO	C6H6	As	Cd	Pb	Ni
Albania												
Andorra	1	1	2	1		1	1					
Austria	127	68	106	144	30	66	27	21	13	14	13	13
Belgium	78	81	39	129	23	27	22	33	30	30	32	30
Bosnia and Herzegovina	20	13	21	22		22	14					
Bulgaria	40	9	20	25	15	28	18	20	7	12	11	7
Croatia	13	14	13	14	6	8	4	3	2	2	2	2
Cyprus	3	4	3	3	1	3	3	1	2	2	2	2
Czechia	145	89	65	94	54	60	21	41	54	54	54	54
Denmark	6	8	8	13	2	4	6	2	3	3	3	3
Estonia	7	7	9	9	5	9	7	4	5	5	5	5
Finland	39	21	16	35	9	14		2	5	5	2	5
France	343	203	300	375	50	84	14	51	49	49	49	50
Germany	379	284	275	625	99	107	86	105	103	103	103	103
Greece	22	11	16	17	1	10	7	8	2	2	2	2
Hungary	25	14	15	16	18	23	19	15	15	15	15	15
Iceland	7	7		7		12	1					
Ireland	53	47	17	31	5	15	5	2	5	5	5	5
Italy	565	310	347	621	167	210	189	244	142	142	135	135
Kosovo	11	11	6	6		3	5					
Latvia	8	5	8	7	7	4	3	7	5	5	5	5
Liechtenstein												
Lithuania	15	8	13	17		13	9	1	5	5	5	5
Luxembourg	6	4	5	117	2	1	2		2	2	2	2
Malta	4	5	4	5	2	4	2	2	2	2	2	2
Montenegro	7	2	3	6		3	5					
Netherlands	65	46	43	70	3	13	6	9	2	2	2	2
North Macedonia	11	13	19	18		16	16					
Norway	54	52	9	46	7	8	1	8	4	4	2	4
Poland	248	133	98	137	165	101	65	69	59	59	59	59
Portugal	40	18	35	55	1	17	13	4	1	1	1	1
Romania	73	17	58	63	3	83	57	13	24	30	30	26
Serbia	10	2	8	15		15	17		2	2	2	2
Slovakia	47	46	22	39	20	19	17	15	8	8	8	8
Slovenia	20	18	10	11	4	3		2	5	5	5	5
Spain	475	289	423	507	96	402	204	126	108	108	111	108
Sweden	61	39	44	109	3	44	3	8	4	4	4	4
Switzerland	29	8	30	32		8	9	3		13	13	
Türkiye	223	115	118	165		204	100					

The countries included in this report and that, therefore, appear in Figure 1, are those with the obligation to report data under the AAQD or that have voluntary reported data. These countries are the EU-27 (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta,

the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden); the five other member countries of the EEA (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and Türkiye) that, together with the EU-27 form the EEA-32; the six EEA's cooperating countries from the Western Balkans (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo under UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia) that, together with the EEA-32 form the EEA-38; and the voluntary reporting country of Andorra.

The air quality data are stored at the EEA's e-reporting database ⁽³⁾. Therefore, this is the source for all maps and figures in the report.

1.1 Particulate matter

For PM₁₀, concentrations above the EU daily limit value (50 µg/m³) were registered at 16 % of the reporting stations. These stations were in 16 countries in EU-27 and in 7 other reporting countries. For PM_{2.5}, concentrations above the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³) were registered at 2 % of the reporting stations. These stations were in 3 countries in EU-27 and in 3 other reporting countries.

The long-term World Health Organization air quality guideline (WHO AQG) level for PM₁₀ (15 µg/m³) was exceeded at 77 % of the stations in 26 countries of the EU-27 and 9 other reporting countries. The long-term WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} (5 µg/m³) was exceeded at 95 % of the stations located in 27 countries of the EU-27 and 9 other reporting countries.

All Member States had met the exposure concentration obligation that was set under the Ambient Air Quality Directive to be attained as of 2015. The exposure concentration obligation reflects exposure of the population to fine particles and required that by 2015 exposure of the general population to PM_{2.5} averaged over the previous 3-year period should not exceed 20 µg/m³. However, the national exposure reduction target was met for all reporting countries except one.

1.2 Ozone

24 % of stations registered concentrations above the EU target value for O₃ (120 µg/m³) for the protection of human health. These stations were located in 18 countries of the EU-27 and 4 other reporting countries. The long-term EU objective (120 µg/m³) was met in only 16 % of the stations. The short-term WHO AQG level for O₃ (100 µg/m³) was exceeded in 91 % of all the reporting stations, and concentrations above the long-term WHO AQG level for O₃ (60 µg/m³) were registered in 97 % of all reporting stations.

³<https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/map/fme/AirQualityExport.htm>

1.3 Nitrogen dioxide

Around 2 % of all the reporting stations recorded concentrations above the EU annual limit value for NO₂ (40 µg/m³). These stations were located in 10 countries of the EU-27 and 1 other reporting countries. 76 % of concentrations above this limit value were observed at traffic stations.

On the contrary, 74 % of stations, located in 27 countries of the EU-27 and 10 other reporting countries reported concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³.

1.4 Benzo[a]pyrene, an indicator for polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

25 % of the stations reported annual mean concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³. They were located in 12 countries in EU-27.

1.5 Sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, benzene and toxic metals

For SO₂, concentrations above the EU daily limit value (125 µg/m³) were registered at 1 % of the reporting stations. These stations were in 0 country of the EU-27 and 4 other reporting countries. However, 6 % of all reporting SO₂ stations measured SO₂ concentrations above the daily WHO AQG level (40 µg/m³). These stations were located in 9 countries of the EU-27 and 8 other reporting countries.

The EU limit value for CO (10 mg/m³), which is the same as the 8-hour WHO AQG level, was exceeded at 0.1 % of the stations. These stations were in 0 country of the EU-27 and 1 other reporting countries.

Concentrations above the EU limit value for C₆H₆ (5 µg/m³) were not observed at any stations.

1 % of stations registered concentrations above the EU target value for As (6 ng/m³). These stations were located in 3 countries of the EU-27 and 0 other reporting countries. For Cd, concentrations above the EU target value (5 ng/m³) were registered at 0.1 % of the stations located in 1 countries of the EU-27 and 0 other reporting countries. The EU target value for Ni (20 ng/m³) was exceeded at 0.6 % of the stations. These stations were located in 4 countries of the EU-27 and 0 other reporting countries. Pb concentrations above the limit value (0.5 µg/m³) were measured at 0 % of the stations located in 0 countries of the EU-27 and 0 other reporting countries.

1.6 Editorial note

Values in Table 4 in the Annex are considered outliers and were not taken into account for the analysis presented in this report.

Due to a problem in the calculation of the aggregates, the figures for the daily limit value for PM10 (Figure 3 and Figure 4) and the daily WHO AQG level for PM10 (Figure 9 and Figure 10) do not show data for Switzerland for the year 2020. This situation is repeated in the figures for the daily WHO AQG level for PM2.5 (Figure 15 and Figure 16) where data for Switzerland and Estonia are also missing for the year 2020.

2 Introduction

The 2022 *Status report of air quality in Europe* presents summarized information on the air quality data reported as measurements data under the 2023 September reporting cycle (validated assessment data for 2022, deadline of submission 30 September 2023). This report aims at informing on the 2022 status of ambient air quality in Europe and on progress towards meeting the air quality standards established for the protection of health in the Ambient Air Quality Directives (EU, 2004, 2008) (Table 1) and the World Health Organization air quality guideline levels (WHO, 2000, 2006, 2021) (Table 2)⁽⁴⁾.

This report builds on the former EEA “Air quality in Europe report” (EEA, 2020) content, figures and maps regarding the status of monitored air quality in Europe. It provides:

- a European overview of the 2022 monitoring stations reported, and of their concentrations in relation to the EU legal standards and WHO AQG levels for each pollutant;
- a map with the 2022 concentrations at station level for each pollutant;
- a boxplot graph summarizing for each country the range of concentrations (highlighting the lowest, highest, average and the 25 and 75 percentiles) for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, O₃ and BaP.

Furthermore, it provides:

- maps with the situation at station level for the previous three years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed;
- heatmaps with the evolution of the mean and the maximum measured concentrations at country level since 2000 (or since when available).

⁴Nevertheless, in this report the following standards and guideline levels are not analysed: information and alert thresholds for O₃, alert threshold for NO₂, and alert threshold for SO₂ in Table 1; and hourly air quality guideline level for NO₂, 10 minutes air quality guideline level for SO₂, and hourly air quality guideline level for CO in Table 2.

Table 1: Air quality standards for the protection of health, as given in the EU Ambient Air Quality Directives

Pollutant	Averaging period	Legal nature and concentration	Comments
PM ₁₀	1 day	Limit value: 50 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 35 days per year
	Calendar year	Limit value: 40 µg/m ³	
PM _{2.5}	Calendar year	Limit value: 25 µg/m ³	Stage 1
		Indicative limit value: 20 µg/m ³	Stage 2: indicative limit value to be reviewed by the Commission in 2013. It remained unchanged after that revision
	Exposure concentration obligation: 20 µg/m ³	Average Exposure Indicator (AEI) ^(a) in 2015 (2013-2015 average)	
	National Exposure reduction target: 0-20 percentage reduction in exposure	AEI ^(a) in 2020, the percentage reduction depends on the initial AEI	
O ₃	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	Target value: 120 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 25 days/year, averaged over 3 years ^(b)
		Long term objective: 120 µg/m ³	
	1 hour	Information threshold: 180 µg/m ³ Alert threshold: 240 µg/m ³	
NO ₂	1 hour	Limit value: 200 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 18 hours per year
		Alert threshold: 400 µg/m ³	To be measured over 3 consecutive hours over 100 km ² or an entire zone
	Calendar year	Limit value: 40 µg/m ³	
BaP	Calendar year	Target value: 1 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
SO ₂	1 hour	Limit value: 350 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 24 hours per year
		Alert threshold: 500 µg/m ³	To be measured over 3 consecutive hours over 100 km ² or an entire zone
	1 day	Limit value: 125 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 3 days per year
CO	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	Limit value: 10 mg/m ³	
C ₆ H ₆	Calendar year	Limit value: 5 µg/m ³	
Pb	Calendar year	Limit value: 0.5 µg/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
As	Calendar year	Target value: 6 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
Cd	Calendar year	Target value: 5 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
Ni	Calendar year	Target value: 20 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀

Notes:

^a AEI: based upon measurements in urban background locations established for this purpose by the Member States, assessed as a 3-year running annual mean.

^b In the context of this report, only the maximum daily 8-hour means in 2022 are considered, so no average over the period 2020 - 2022 is presented.

Sources:

EU (2004, 2008).

Table 2: WHO air quality guideline (AQG) levels and estimated reference levels (RL) ^(a)

Pollutant	Averaging period	AQG	RL	Comments
PM ₁₀	1 day	45 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
	Calendar year	15 µg/m ³		Updated 2021 guideline
PM _{2.5}	1 day	15 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
	Calendar year	5 µg/m ³		Updated 2021 guideline
O ₃	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	100 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
	Peak season ^(b)	60 µg/m ³		New 2021 guideline
NO ₂	1 hour	200 µg/m ³		
	1 day	25 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). New 2021 guideline
	Calendar year	10 µg/m ³		Updated 2021 guideline
BaP	Calendar year		0.12 ng/m ³	
SO ₂	10 minutes	500 µg/m ³		
	1 day	40 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
CO	1 hour	30 mg/m ³		
	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	10 mg/m ³		
	1 day	4 mg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). New 2021 guideline
C ₆ H ₆	Calendar year		1.7 µg/m ³	
Pb	Calendar year	0.5 µg/m ³		
As	Calendar year		6.6 ng/m ³	
Cd	Calendar year	5 ng/m ³ ^(c)		
Ni	Calendar year		25 ng/m ³	

Notes:

^a As WHO has not set an AQG level for BaP, C₆H₆, As and Ni, the RL was estimated assuming an acceptable risk of additional lifetime cancer risk of approximately 1 in 100 000.

^b Average of daily maximum 8-hour mean concentration in the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running average O₃ concentration.

^c AQG set to prevent any further increase of Cd in agricultural soil, likely to increase the dietary intake of future generations.

Sources:

WHO (2000, 2006, 2021).

Box 1.1 Classification of monitoring stations and criteria used for the assessment

Fixed sampling points in Europe are situated at different types of stations following rules for macro- and micro-scale siting. Briefly, depending on the predominant emission sources, stations are classified as follows:

- traffic stations: located in close proximity to a single major road;
- industrial stations: located in close proximity to an industrial area or an industrial source;
- background stations: where pollution levels are representative of the average exposure of the general population or vegetation.

Depending on the distribution/density of buildings, the area surrounding the station is classified as follows:

- urban: continuously built-up urban area;
- suburban: largely built-up urban area;
- rural: all other areas.

In general, for the pollutants considered in this report, monitoring stations have to fulfil the criterion of reporting more than 75 % of valid data out of all the possible data in a year to be included in this assessment. The Ambient Air Quality Directive sets, for compliance purposes, the objective of a minimum data capture of 90 % for monitoring stations, but, for assessment purposes, a coverage of 75 % allows more stations to be taken into account without a significant increase in monitoring uncertainties. For benzene, As, Cd, Ni and BaP, the general amount of valid data is 13% (according to the air quality objectives for indicative measurements). The exceptions to the general rule are PM and lead random fixed measurements, for which the required amount of valid data for the analysis is 13 %. Reporting stations not fulfilling the minimum data coverage could be found at the [Annual AQ statistics table](#).

Measurement data are rounded following the general recommendations under (EU, 2011). The number of considered decimals are indicated in the legend of the corresponding maps.

The assessments, in the cases of PM and SO₂, do not account for the fact that the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2008) provides Member States with the possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting under specific circumstances.

3 Status of particulate matter ambient air concentrations

3.1 Status of PM₁₀ concentrations

The EEA received PM₁₀ data for 2022, with sufficient valid measurements (a general minimum coverage of 75 % and of 13 % for fixed random measurements) from 3280 stations for the calculation of annual mean concentrations and from 3262 stations in relation to the daily limit value. The stations were located in all the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

Sixteen countries in EU-27, and seven other reporting countries reported PM₁₀ concentrations above the EU daily limit value of 50 µg/m³ (Figure 2). This was the case for 16 % (506) of reporting stations. In total, 96 % of those stations were either urban (84 %) or suburban (12 %). The stricter value of the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ daily mean (45 µg/m³) was exceeded at 68 % (2230) of the stations in all the reporting countries (Figure 8).

Concentrations above the PM₁₀ annual limit value (40 µg/m³) were monitored in 5 % (177 stations) of all the reporting stations, located in 4 countries in EU-27, and 5 other reporting countries. The stricter value of the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ annual mean (15 µg/m³) was exceeded at 77 % (2531) of the stations in all the reporting countries, except in Estonia and Iceland (Figure 5).

Figure 2: Map and boxplot of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2022 - daily limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2022. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The map shows the 90.4 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations, representing the 36th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the PM₁₀ daily limit value, allowing 35 exceedances of the 50 µg/m³ threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 90.4 percentile of daily mean concentration values corresponding to the 36th highest daily mean in a complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2022 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) 90.4 percentile values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The daily limit value set by EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

The highest value in the boxplot, Türkiye (214 µg/m³), has not been included in the graph for representation purposes.

Figure 3 shows the maps of the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the PM₁₀ daily limit value) for four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data on the central data repository (CDR).

Figure 3: Maps of PM₁₀ concentrations (daily limit value) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 4. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 4: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (daily limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 5: Map and boxplot of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2022 - annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2022. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The last two colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³). The first colour category indicate stations reporting values below the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ (15 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2022 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value set by EU legislation is marked by the upper continuous horizontal line. The WHO AQG level is marked by the lower dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 6 shows the maps of PM₁₀ annual mean concentrations at station level for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 6: Maps of PM₁₀ concentrations (annual limit value) for the last 4 years

Maps for years before 2020 are different to the ones published in previous reports because the bands in the legend have been modified to accommodate the 2021 WHO AQG level.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) annual mean PM₁₀ concentrations at country level are shown in figure 7. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 7: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) PM₁₀ annual mean concentrations (annual limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 8: Map of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2022 - daily WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2022. The map shows the 99 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the daily WHO AQG level (45 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Figure 9 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 9: Maps of PM₁₀ concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 10. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 10: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

3.2 Status of PM_{2.5} concentrations

Regarding PM_{2.5}, data with a general minimum coverage of 75 %, and of 13 % for fixed random stations, of valid data were received from 2022 stations for the calculation of annual mean concentrations and from 2011 stations in relation to the short-term WHO AQG level. These stations were located in all the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

The PM_{2.5} concentrations were higher than the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³) in three countries in EU-27 and three other reporting countries (Figure 11). These concentrations above the limit value were registered in 2 % of all the reporting stations and occurred primarily (93 % of cases) in urban (78 %) or suburban (15 %) areas.

The WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} annual mean (5 µg/m³) was exceeded at 95 % of the stations, located in 36 of the 37 countries reporting PM_{2.5} data (Figure 11). Iceland did not report any concentrations above the WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5}.

Although the EU has not set any short-term standard for PM_{2.5}, the WHO defined in 2021 a daily AQG level of 15 µg/m³, expressed as percentile 99. It was exceeded at 97 % (1960 stations) of the stations in all the reporting countries (Figure 14).

Figure 11: Map and boxplot of PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2022 - annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM_{2.5} in 2022. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The last two colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the EU indicative annual limit value (20 µg/m³) or the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations reporting values below the WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} (5 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13% in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2022 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value and the indicative annual limit value set by EU legislation are marked by the upper continuous horizontal lines at 25 and 20, respectively. The WHO AQG level is marked by the lower dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 12 shows the maps of measured PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 12: Maps of PM_{2.5} concentrations (annual limit value) for the last 4 years

Maps for years before 2020 are different to the ones published in previous reports because the bands in the legend have been modified to accommodate the 2021 WHO AQG level.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 13. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 13: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations (annual limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 14: Map of PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2022 - daily WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of PM_{2.5} in 2022. The map shows the 99 percentile of the PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the daily WHO AQG level (15 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Figure 15 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 15: Maps of PM_{2.5} concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 16. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 16: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

3.3 PM_{2.5} average exposure indicator

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2008) also sets two additional targets for PM_{2.5}, the exposure concentration obligation (ECO) and the national exposure reduction target (NERT) (Table 1). Both targets are based on the average exposure indicator (AEI), calculated at national level. The AEI is an average of concentration levels (over a 3-year period) measured at urban background stations (representative of general urban population exposure) selected for this purpose by every national authority. The reference year for the AEI is 2010 (average 2008-2010), but the Ambient Air Quality Directive offered two additional alternatives when data are not available for 2008: (1) an alternative AEI 2010, with a 2-year average (2009 and 2010) instead of the 3-year average; or (2) the AEI 2011 (average 2009-2011). The exception is Croatia for which 2015 is the AEI reference year (average 2013-2015). The data presented here are analysed with reference to the official AEI reported by each country and stored in EEA's vocabulary ⁽⁵⁾ and presented in Table 5 in the Annex.

Figure 17 assesses PM_{2.5} levels against the ECO threshold. It shows the AEI reported for 2022 (average 2020-2022) and the situation in relation to the ECO. The bars show the AEI 2022 as reported by countries under data flow G (Information on the attainment of environmental objectives) according to Article 12 of IPR Decision 2011/850/EU, while the dots show the 3-year (2020-2022) average concentrations from measurements at all urban and suburban background stations with 75 % data coverage. This calculation, covering the urban and suburban background stations, has been used in previous *Air quality in Europe* reports as an approximation of the AEI and is presented here for comparison with the information presented in those reports. The calculation using reported urban and suburban background stations is also made for the rest of the non-EU countries.

In Figure 17, the vertical line represents the ECO threshold, set at 20 µg/m³. For those countries whose bars are to the right of the vertical line, the AEI is above the ECO (based on reported information in data-flow G). For those countries whose dots are to the right of the vertical line, the 3 year average calculated from reported urban and suburban background stations is above the ECO.

⁵<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/aq/exposurereductiontarget/view>.

Figure 17: Average exposure indicator in 2022 and exposure concentration obligation

Note: The bars show the average exposure indicator (AEI) calculated in 2022 (averages 2020–2022) as reported by countries under data flow G (Information on the attainment of environmental objectives) according to Article 12 of IPR Decision 2011/850/EU. The dots show the 3 year (2020–2022) average of all urban and suburban background PM2.5 concentrations (for stations with at least 75 % of data coverage) in all reporting countries, to facilitate comparison with information provided in previous Air quality in Europe reports. The vertical line represents the exposure concentration obligation (ECO) for the countries in EU–27, set at 20 µg/m³, to be achieved as of 2015.

Figure 18 shows the situation per country in relation to the NERT. The total stacked bar (both blue and orange parts) represents the initial baseline AEI for 2010 or 2011 as reported by each country expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (see Table 5 in Annex). The blue part is the latest reported AEI for 2022, as it can also be seen in figure 17 (if a country has not reported data for the year of analysis, only the orange bar will be shown). The triangles indicate the NERT level to be attained from 2020 onwards. Figure 18 shows those countries that have reduced their AEI below their corresponding NERT, estimated from their initial AEI baseline, (those who have reported data, and therefore have blue part, and whose triangles is over the orange bar) and those that did not (triangles over the blue part of the bar).

Figure 18: Reduction in AEI 2022 in relation to AEI 2011 and distance to the national exposure reduction target

Note: The total stacked bar indicate the initial baseline AEI for 2010 or 2011 (AEI 2015 in the case of Croatia, see the main text).
 Triangles indicate the NERT to be met in 2022 applying the percentage reduction to the AEI baseline.
 If the triangle is over the orange part of the stack bar, the NERT was achieved in 2022,
 if the triangle is over the blue part of the bar, the NERT is not met.

4 Status of ozone ambient air concentrations

Data for O₃ were reported from 2189 stations for the calculation of EU standards, from 2189 stations in relation to the short-term WHO AQG level, and from 2083 stations for the long-term WHO AQG level. These stations were located in all the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

18 countries in EU-27 and 4 other reporting countries registered concentrations above the O₃ target value threshold (120 µg/m³) more than 25 times this year (Figure 19). In total, 24 % of all stations reporting O₃ showed concentrations above the target value threshold for the protection of human health. In addition, only 16 % (345) of all stations fulfilled the long-term objective (120 µg/m³). 86 % of the stations with values above the long-term objective were background stations.

9 % (193) of all stations and only 18 of the 554 reported rural background stations had values below the short-term WHO AQG value for O₃ (100 µg/m³) (Figure 22), set for the protection of human health. The long-term, peak season⁽⁶⁾, WHO AQG level (60 µg/m³) was exceeded in 97 % (2024) of all stations located in 27 countries in EU-27 and 8 other reporting countries. Only 1 of the 534 reported rural background stations had values below this AQG level (Figure 25).

⁶The peak season is calculated for each station as the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration in the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running-average O₃ concentration. That means that, for each station, twelve 6-months running averages of the daily 8-h max are calculated (1 August YY-1 to 31 January YY, ..., 1 January YY to 30 June YY, ..., 1 July YY to 31 December YY) and the maximum of those 12 values is selected as the peak season concentration. Please check also Data Dictionary - Vocabulary (<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabularyconcept/aq/aggregationprocess/P1Y-maxP6M-P8H-dmax/view?vocabularyFolder.workingCopy=false&facet=HTML+Representation>).

Figure 19: Map and boxplot of O₃ concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2022. The map shows the 93.2 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean, representing the 26th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the O₃ target value. At sites marked with the last two colour categories, the 26th highest daily O₃ concentrations were above the 120 µg/m³ threshold, implying values above the target value threshold. Please note that the legal definition of the target value considers not only 1 year but the average over 3 years. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration values, corresponding to the 26th highest daily maximum of the running 8-hour mean in a complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2022 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The target value threshold set by the EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. Please note that the legal definition of the target value considers not only 1 year but the average over 3 years. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 20 shows the maps of the observed 93.2 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations (O₃ target value) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change

in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 20: Maps of O₃ concentrations (related to the target value) for the last 4 years

Note: Please be aware that the TV considers the average over 3 years and the maps only show the situation for one specific year.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) O₃ concentrations (93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration, target value) at country level are shown in figure 21. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020), especially for O₃ as higher ambient air temperature leads to enhanced photochemical reactions and O₃ formation.

Figure 21: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) O₃ concentrations (93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration, related to the target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 22: Map of O₃ concentrations in 2022 - short-term WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2022. The map shows the 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the short-term WHO AQG level (100 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 23 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations (equivalent to the short-term WHO AQG level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 23: Maps of O₃ concentrations (short-term WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) of 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 24. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 24: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 25: Map of peak season O₃ concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2022. The map shows the average of the daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration in the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running-average O₃ concentration. The first colour category represents stations fulfilling the peak season O₃ AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 26 shows the maps of the peak season O₃ concentrations (equivalent to the long-term WHO AQG level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 26: Maps of peak season O₃ concentrations for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) peak season O₃ concentrations at country level are shown in figure 27. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 27: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) peak season O₃ concentrations per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

5 Status of nitrogen dioxide ambient air concentrations

The reporting countries shown in Figure 1 submitted NO₂ data from 3605 stations for the annual limit value, 3169 stations for the hourly limit value, and 3165 stations for the daily WHO AQG level.

10 of the countries in EU-27 and 1 other reporting countries (Figure 28) recorded concentrations above the annual limit value (40 µg/m³). This happened in 2 % of all the stations measuring NO₂. On the contrary, 74 % of stations, located in 27 of the countries in EU-27 and 10 other reporting countries reported concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³. Figure 28 shows the measured annual mean NO₂ concentrations.

76 % of all values above the annual limit value were observed at traffic stations. Furthermore, 100 % of the stations with concentrations above the annual limit value were located in urban or suburban areas.

Concentrations above the hourly limit value (200 µg/m³) were observed in 0.8 % (24 stations) of all reporting stations, mostly at urban traffic stations. They were observed in two countries (number stations): Türkiye (twenty-three) and Lithuania (one).

Finally, concentrations above the daily NO₂ WHO AQG level (25 µg/m³) were registered in 78 % (2463 stations) of all the reporting stations in 27 of the countries in EU-27 and 10 other reporting countries (Figure 31).

Figure 28: Map and boxplot of NO₂ concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of NO₂ in 2022. The last two colour categories correspond to values above the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³), while the first colour category indicates stations reporting values below the WHO AQG level for NO₂ (10 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on the annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2022 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The limit value set by EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. The WHO AQG level is marked by the lower dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

The highest value in the boxplot, Türkiye (107 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), has not been included in the graph for representation purposes.

Figure 29 shows the maps of the observed NO_2 annual mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 29: Map of NO_2 concentrations (annual mean) for the last 4 years

Maps for years before 2020 are different to the ones published in previous reports because the bands in the legend have been modified to accommodate the 2021 WHO AQG level.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) NO_2 annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 30. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 30: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) NO₂ annual mean concentrations (annual limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 31: Map of NO₂ concentrations in 2022 - daily WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of NO₂ in 2022. The map shows the 99 percentile of the NO₂ daily mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the daily WHO AQG level (25 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 32 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of NO₂ daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG level for NO₂ daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 32: Maps of NO₂ concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of NO₂ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 33. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 33: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of NO₂ daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

6 Status of benzo[a]pyrene ambient air concentrations

A total of 798 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1 reported BaP data with sufficient data coverage.

12 countries measured concentrations above 1.0 ng/m^3 (Figure 34). These were measured at 25 % of the reported BaP measurement stations (Figure 34), mainly at urban (78 % of all stations with values above 1.0 ng/m^3) and suburban (18 %) stations.

Regarding the reference level, all reporting countries, except for Cyprus, Portugal and Sweden have at least one station with concentrations above 0.12 ng/m^3 . Only 21 % of the reported stations had annual concentrations below the reference level.

Figure 34: Map and boxplot of BaP concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of BaP in 2022. The first colour category correspond to concentrations under the estimated reference RL (0.12 ng/m³). The last colour category correspond to concentrations exceeding the 2004 Ambient Air Quality Directive target value of 1 ng/m³. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data, as daily, weekly or monthly measurements, have been included in the map.

BaP concentrations in relation to the annual limit value in 2022 and number of stations considered for each country

Note: The graph is based on the annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2022 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in ng/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The upper horizontal line marks the concentration of 1.0 ng/m³. The lower horizontal line marks the estimated air quality RL. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

The highest value in the boxplot, Poland (9 ng/m³), has not been included in the graph for representation purposes.

Figure 35 shows the maps of the observed BaP annual mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 35: Maps of BaP concentrations (annual mean) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2005 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) BaP annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 36. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 36: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) BaP annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2005

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7 Status of sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, benzene and toxic metals ambient air concentrations

7.1 Sulphur dioxide

The reporting countries shown in Figure 1 reported measurements of SO₂ from 1615 stations for the hourly limit value and 1612 stations for the daily limit value.

13 stations ⁽⁷⁾ registered concentrations above the hourly limit value (350 µg/m³); and 16 stations ⁽⁸⁾ registered concentrations above the daily limit of 125 µg/m³ for SO₂ (Figure 37).

On the contrary, 92 (6 %) of all the stations reporting SO₂ levels, located in 17 reporting countries ⁽⁹⁾, measured SO₂ concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 40 µg/m³ for daily mean concentrations ⁽¹⁰⁾.

⁷Bosnia and Herzegovina (eight), Türkiye (four) and Serbia (one)

⁸Bosnia and Herzegovina (nine), Türkiye (four), North Macedonia (two) and Serbia (one).

⁹All reporting countries except Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden and Switzerland.

¹⁰Although the WHO AQG level for daily means refers to the percentile 99 (3-4 exceedance days), here we have used the percentile 99.18 (3 exceedance days), so the daily WHO AQG level can be directly compared with the EU daily LV.

Figure 37: Map of SO₂ daily concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of SO₂ in 2022. The map shows the percentile 99.18 of SO₂ daily means, indicating 3 exceedance days. It relates to the EU daily limit value (125 µg/m³) and to the WHO daily AQG level (40 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 38 shows the maps of the observed SO₂ daily mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 38: Maps of SO₂ concentrations (daily mean) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) SO₂ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 39. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 39: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) SO₂ 99.18 percentile of daily mean concentrations (EU LV (125 µg/m³) and WHO AQG level (40 µg/m³)) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7.2 Carbon monoxide

All reporting countries shown in Figure 1 measured CO data from 967 operational stations for the daily limit value and from 972 stations for the daily WHO AQG level. Only 1 stations (Figure 40) registered concentrations above the CO limit daily value (10 mg/m^3) and the WHO AQG level for the maximum daily 8-hour mean. These stations were located in Serbia (one).

1 stations registered concentrations above the daily WHO AQG level (4 mg/m^3). They were located in Türkiye (one) (Figure 42).

Figure 40: Map of CO concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of CO in 2022. The map shows the CO maximum daily 8-hour mean. The last two colour categories correspond to values above the EU annual limit value and the WHO AQG (10 mg/m^3). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

When concentrations are below the 'lower assessment threshold' (LAT), air quality can be assessed by means of only modelling or objective estimates. At 940 stations (97 % of locations), maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations of CO were below the LAT of 5 mg/m^3 (first two colour categories in Figure 40).

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) CO maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 41. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 41: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) CO maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations (limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 42: Map of daily CO concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of CO in 2022. The map shows the 99 percentile of CO daily concentrations, meaning 3–4 exceedance days. The first colour category corresponds to values below the WHO AQG level (4 mg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 43 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of CO daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG for CO daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 43: Maps of CO concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of CO daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 44. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 44: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of CO daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7.3 Benzene

C₆H₆ measurements were reported from a total of 819 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

Concentrations above the limit value for C₆H₆ (5 µg/m³) were not observed at any stations. At 96 % of locations, annual mean concentrations of C₆H₆ were below the LAT of 2 µg/m³ (first two colour categories in Figure 45).

Regarding the estimated WHO reference level (1.7 µg/m³), 6 % of all stations reported concentrations above this reference level, distributed across 13 European countries ⁽¹¹⁾ (Figure 45).

Figure 45: Map of C₆H₆ concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of C₆H₆ in 2022. The last colour category correspond to concentrations above the limit value of 5 µg/m³. The first colour category correspond to concentrations under the estimated WHO RL (1.7 µg/m³). Only stations reporting more than 50 % of valid data have been included in the map.

¹¹Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Romania and Spain

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) C₆H₆ annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 46. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 46: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) C₆H₆ annual mean concentrations (limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7.4 Toxic metals

Data for **Arsenic (As)** were reported from 668 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. 6 stations measured concentrations above the target value (6 ng/m^3), located in: Belgium (two), Finland (two) and Poland (two), and 3 of these were industrial. Concentrations of As below the LAT (2.4 ng/m^3) were reported at 95 % of the stations (Figure 47).

Figure 47: Map of As concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of As in 2022. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the EU target value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) As annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 48. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 48: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) As annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Cadmium (Cd) data were reported from 693 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. Concentrations above the target value (5 ng/m^3) were measured at 1 station located in: Bulgaria (one). At the great majority of stations (98 %), Cd concentrations were below the LAT (2 ng/m^3) (Figure 49).

Figure 49: Map of Cd concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of Cd in 2022. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the target value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) Cd annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 50. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 50: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) Cd annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Lead (Pb) data were reported from 684 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. 0 stations located in: NO result reported Pb concentrations above the $0.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ limit value. 683 stations (100 % of the total) reported Pb concentrations below the LAT of $0.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 51: Map of Pb concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of Pb in 2022. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the EU annual limit value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map. Source: EEA, 2022.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) Pb annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 52. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 52: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) Pb annual mean concentrations (limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Nickel (Ni) data were reported from 664 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. Concentrations were above the target value of 20 ng/m³ at 4 stations in: Finland (one), France (one), Germany (one) and Italy (one), 3 of which were industrial. About 98 % of the stations reported Ni concentrations below the LAT of 10 ng/m³ (Figure 53).

Figure 53: Map of Ni concentrations in 2022

Note: Observed concentrations of Ni in 2022. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the target value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) Ni annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 54. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 54: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) Ni annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

8 Abbreviations, units and symbols

$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$: microgram(s) per cubic metre

AAQD: Ambient Air Quality Directives

AEI: Average exposure indicator for PM_{2.5} concentrations

AQG: Air quality guideline

As: Arsenic

BaP: Benzo[a]pyrene

C₆H₆: Benzene

Cd: Cadmium

CDR: Central data repository

CO: Carbon monoxide

ECO: Exposure concentration obligation

EEA: European Environment Agency

ETC HE: European Topic Centre on Human health and the Environment

EU: European Union

LAT: Lower assessment threshold

LV: limit value

mg/m^3 : milligram(s) per cubic metre

NERT: National exposure reduction target

ng/m^3 : nanogram(s) per cubic metre

Ni: Nickel

NO₂: Nitrogen dioxide

O₃: Ozone

Pb: Lead

PM: Particulate matter

PM_{2.5}: Particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 µm or less

PM₁₀: Particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm or less

RL: Reference level

SO₂: Sulphur dioxide

TV: target value

WHO: World Health Organization

9 Annex

Data included in this report was received by 05 March 2024 from the reporting countries. By that date the number of stations by country aggregation reporting each pollutant is summarized in Table 3. Data from stations that do not fulfil the criteria from Box 1.1 are excluded from this report.

Table 3: Number of stations reporting 2022 data with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, by 05 March 2024

Countries	PM10	PM2.5	O3	NO2	BaP	SO2	CO	C6H6	As	Cd	Pb	Ni
EU27	2907	1798	2012	3288	791	1372	809	808	662	674	667	658
EEA32	3220	1980	2169	3538	798	1604	920	819	666	691	682	662
Total	3280	2022	2228	3606	798	1664	978	819	668	693	684	664

Data not included in this report is summarized in Table 4:

Table 4: Reporting outliers of 2022 air quality data by 05 March 2024

Country	Station Eol Code	Pollutant	Aggregation(*)	Year	Value	Units	Data Coverage
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA0055A	SO2	P1Y	2022	101	ug/m3	86
Spain	ES1847A	PM2.5	P1Y-P1D-per99	2022	341	ug/m3	21
Türkiye	TRO047A	SO2	P1Y-day-max-per99.18	2022	524	ug/m3	94
Türkiye	TRO049A	PM2.5	P1Y-P1D-per99	2022	268	ug/m3	93

(*) <https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/aq/aggregationprocess/view>

The following table (Table 5) summarizes the average exposure indicator (AEI) by country.

Table 5: AEI calculated at national level

Country	Reference years	Initial AEI	Percentage of reduction	NERT
Austria	2009-2011	17.8	15.00	15.1
Belgium	2009-2011	19.0	20.00	15.2
Bulgaria	2008-2010	36.0	50.00	18.0
Croatia	2013-2015	20.6	20.00	16.5
Cyprus	2009-2011	21.5	20.00	17.2
Czechia	2009-2011	26.6	32.30	18.0
Denmark	2008-2010	14.0	15.00	11.9
Estonia	2009-2011	5.9	0.00	8.5
Finland	2009-2011	8.3	0.00	8.5
France	2009-2011	17.3	15.00	14.7
Germany	2008-2010	16.0	15.00	13.6
Greece	2008-2010	17.0	15.00	14.5
Hungary	2009-2010	21.0	20.00	16.8
Iceland	2008-2010	10.8	10.00	9.7
Ireland	2009-2011	10.2	10.00	9.2
Italy	2009-2011	19.9	20.00	15.9
Latvia	2008-2010	18.0	20.00	14.4
Lithuania	2009-2011	12.3	10.00	11.1
Luxembourg	2009-2010	17.4	15.00	14.8
Malta	2009-2011	13.2	15.00	11.2
Netherlands	2009-2011	17.0	15.00	14.5
Norway	2009-2011	10.0	10.00	9.0
Poland	2009-2011	27.8	35.25	18.0
Portugal	2008-2010	9.7	10.00	8.7
Romania	2009-2011	18.4	20.00	14.7
Slovakia	2009-2011	24.4	26.20	18.0
Slovenia	2009-2011	21.7	20.00	17.4
Spain	2009-2011	14.1	15.00	12.0
Sweden	2009-2011	6.6	0.00	8.5

Table 6 summarizes the number of sampling points per country with air quality levels above specific air quality objectives summarized through out this report. Sampling points that do not fulfil the criteria from Box 1.1 are excluded.

Table 6: Number of sampling points above air quality levels/objectives per reporting country

Levels/Objectives	Andorra	Austria	Belgium	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bulgaria	Croatia	Cyprus	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Iceland	Ireland	Italy	Kosovo	Latvia	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Malta	Montenegro	Netherlands	North Macedonia	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Serbia	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Türkiye	
PM ₁₀ daily LV (50 µg/m ³)	0	0	2	16	12	1	1	3	0	0	0	3	0	10	3	0	0	117	3	0	0	0	1	5	0	10	2	43	0	3	7	3	1	62	6	0	192	
PM ₁₀ daily WHO AQG level (45 µg/m ³)	1	14	66	20	37	7	3	102	1	3	20	157	91	20	18	3	16	497	10	6	12	2	4	6	37	11	36	236	40	63	9	35	14	363	44	6	220	
PM ₁₀ annual LV (40 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	7	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	19	0	0	135	
PM ₁₀ annual WHO AQG level (15 µg/m ³)	1	70	67	19	36	9	3	124	3	0	2	241	184	21	23	0	11	524	11	7	11	4	4	7	54	11	22	243	37	66	10	44	19	381	33	8	221	
PM _{2.5} annual LV (25 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	
PM _{2.5} annual WHO AQG level (5 µg/m ³)	1	67	75	13	9	14	4	88	8	1	4	195	283	11	14	0	43	309	11	5	8	4	5	2	46	13	42	133	15	17	2	46	18	277	16	8	115	
PM _{2.5} daily WHO AQG level (15 µg/m ³)	1	67	81	13	9	14	4	89	8	3	14	196	284	11	14	1	47	308	10	5	8	4	5	2	46	13	43	133	16	17	2	46	18	275	33	8	112	
O ₃ max daily 8h mean TV (120 µg/m ³)	0	33	0	7	1	2	2	20	0	0	0	76	59	8	6	0	0	196	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	5	8	6	6	3	4	43	0	20	17	
O ₃ long-term objective (120 µg/m ³)	1	102	39	16	8	12	3	64	8	5	3	280	273	13	15	0	12	307	0	2	4	4	3	2	43	8	7	93	29	27	8	20	10	321	12	30	59	
O ₃ short-term WHO AQG level (100 µg/m ³)	1	106	39	17	10	12	3	65	8	6	4	282	275	14	15	0	13	330	0	4	10	5	3	3	43	10	6	98	31	40	8	22	10	387	16	30	70	
O ₃ peak season WHO AQG level (60 µg/m ³)	2	104	38	10	16	8	3	64	8	9	16	275	269	12	13	0	10	338	0	1	13	5	3	1	43	9	7	95	30	50	8	19	8	407	22	30	78	
NO ₂ annual LV (40 µg/m ³)	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	3	3	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	43	
NO ₂ annual WHO AQG level (10 µg/m ³)	1	109	115	18	19	11	2	68	4	1	14	261	516	15	16	1	21	479	6	5	10	105	4	6	62	14	36	103	35	55	14	23	8	295	45	24	151	
NO ₂ hourly LV (200 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23
NO ₂ daily WHO AQG level (25 µg/m ³)	1	113	82	20	19	12	2	76	9	5	25	287	327	16	16	2	28	477	4	6	13	5	4	6	70	13	42	108	34	51	14	25	8	321	45	28	149	
BaP annual LV (1 ng/m ³)	0	1	0	0	3	2	0	19	0	0	2	1	0	0	4	0	0	16	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	142	0	0	0	10	1	0	0	0	0	
BaP annual WHO AQG level (0.12 ng/m ³)	0	30	17	0	12	5	0	54	1	4	7	29	76	1	18	0	3	138	0	6	0	2	1	0	1	0	5	165	0	3	0	20	4	30	0	0	0	
SO ₂ hourly LV (350 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
SO ₂ daily LV (125 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
SO ₂ daily WHO AQG level (40 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	17	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	4	2	0	1	4	0	0	2	0	0	45	
CO daily LV (10 mg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CO daily WHO AQG level (4 mg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
C ₆ H ₆ annual WHO RL (1.7 µg/m ³)	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	7	0	0	0	3	2	6	2	0	0	11	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	5	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	
As annual TV (6 ng/m ³)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
As annual LAT (2.4 ng/m ³)	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	

Table 6: Number of sampling points above air quality levels/objectives per reporting country (continued)

Levels/Objectives	Andorra	Austria	Belgium	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bulgaria	Croatia	Cyprus	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Iceland	Ireland	Italy	Kosovo	Latvia	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Malta	Montenegro	Netherlands	North Macedonia	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Serbia	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Türkiye	
Cd annual TV (5 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cd annual LAT (2 ng/m ³)	0	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Pb annual LAT (0.25 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Ni annual TV (20 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ni annual LAT (10 ng/m ³)	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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